

Mapping the manosphere: thematic diffusion and influence across Reddit’s gender-focused communities

Marie Serisier

Online forums do not simply function as echo chambers, they also operate as discursive arenas where a wide array of views on masculinities (cisgender, transgender, heterosexual, or queer) are articulated and debated (Devries et al., 2021; Maloney et al., 2024). As these platforms offer sometimes unmoderated spaces for debating contemporary issues surrounding masculinities, they simultaneously enable the circulation of radical viewpoints that shape public discourse on gender and often reinforce anti-feminist positions. These anti-feminist groups, collectively referred to as the “manosphere”, constitute a “loosely connected network of subreddits, blogs, YouTube channels, and forums”(Horta Ribeiro et al., 2021, p.196). Despite their differences, these communities share a discourse marked by hostility toward women and feminists and promote what Farrell et al. (2019, p.2) call a “flipped narrative”, casting men as the true victims of gender inequality. Our aim is to investigate this presumed “looseness” by examining thematic diffusion across four gender-focused online communities that span the ideological spectrum from anti-feminist to more progressive spaces.

At the core of this online network, Reddit, alongside message boards like 4chan or 8chan, has been extensively scrutinized (Baele et al., 2021), for its decentralized approach to moderation, placing the responsibility for content regulation onto each subreddit’s administration team. Low levels of moderation have been linked to the proliferation of hate speech and the fostering of environments where harassment and gender-based hostility can thrive (Gibson, 2019). As such, Reddit is the home of some of the major groups in the manosphere, making it a particularly relevant site for examining digital gender activism.

This study examines how ideas circulate across subreddit communities. We ask ourselves whether anti-feminist topics diffuse into more neutral or progressive spaces and what defines an influential masculinist actor within these online environments.

Our analysis focuses on four subreddits: r/MensRights, r/TheRedPill, r/PurplePillDebate, and r/MensLib. These communities span across a wide ideological spectrum, from reactionary positions (r/MensRights, r/TheRedPill) to progressive

(r/MensLib) and supposedly neutral ones (r/PurplePillDebate). R/MensRights activists claim to live in a “gynocentric” society and advocate for issues revolving around custody, alimony, and traditional family structures (Dragiewicz, 2011). R/TheRedPill, inspired by a *Matrix* metaphor, presents anti-feminist beliefs as hidden truths discovered through self-help and personal transformation (Cannito & Ferrero Camoletto, 2022; Van Valkenburgh, 2021). The red pill is a symbol of higher knowledge and clairvoyance when the blue pill means staying in a state of unawareness. The claimed goal of r/PurplePillDebate is to offer a space in which the two (blue and red pill) can argue and debate. R/MensLib promotes feminist-aligned understandings of masculinity (LaViolette & Hogan, 2019).

The dataset was collected through the archive repository Academic Torrents, which hosts the deposits from the Pushshift Dataset, a large-scale project to collect and store data from Reddit (Baumgartner et al., 2020). The collected data was already enriched with useful metadata such as timestamps, document ids, authors and for the comments the linked publication id, i.e. the message to which the comment specifically replied to.

The dataset comprises the complete content of the four subreddits from each communities’ inception through to the end of the defined collection period in late 2022. The corpus is thus composed of more than 500 000 posts and 15 million comments. The subreddits’ lifespans vary : r/MensRights began in 2009, r/TheRedPill and r/PurplePillDebate followed, with respective inceptions in 2012 and 2013 and r/MensLib is the most recent community and has been featured on Reddit since 2015. All posts were tagged and parsed using the “english-web” treebank from the udpipe pipeline (Straka & Straková, 2017). A Latent Dirichlet Allocation topic modeling was then trained onto this tagged corpus. To trace ideological diffusion and user mobility, we combined topic-modeling results with a network representation of the full dataset. Nodes represent anonymized users, and edges represent comment interactions (replies to posts or comments), enriched with metadata such as comment id, post link, date and subreddit. We filtered out users with fewer than five interactions, a threshold determined through degree-distribution analysis. The original graph has 383 306 nodes and 10 029 139 edges, whereas the filtered graph has 170 097 nodes and 9 571 262 edges, with only 44.38% of the original nodes kept after the filtering. The resulting graph is directed.

The model was fitted with 200 topics, which were then manually reviewed and sorted into 12 overarching categories. These categories are as follows : “Health”, “Relationships”, “Mental Health”, “Society and Politics”, “Culture & Entertainment”, “Manosphere”, “Education & Learning”, “Science”, “Personal Development & Beauty”, “Gender & Feminism”, “Business & Money”, “Crime & Justice”. Identifying the most predominant topics in each subreddit we find that r/MensLib members are more concerned with topics revolving around gender and feminism, r/MensRights emphasize family and legal matters, r/PurplePillDebate boasts mainly topics about society and politics and r/TheRedPill is dominated by

topics revolving around self-help and seduction. These findings confirm existing literature on anti-feminist digital communities (Mountford, 2018; Schmitz & Kazyak, 2016).

The salience of each topic within each subreddit was measured using a global z-score, derived from the θ values, which represent each topic’s distribution across all documents. For each subreddit, we focused on the most predominant topics, i.e. those with a z-score of at least 1. To examine their temporal dynamics, we identified each topic’s “birth” and “death” by comparing its global average distribution (θ) with a local mean (time and community dependent). A topic’s birth is defined as the first document when its local mean exceeds its global mean, and its death as the last one before the local mean drops below the global mean again. We also define “peak” moments, corresponding to documents in which a topic’s θ reaches its maximum. These documents allow us to trace the authors involved and analyze their trajectories.

LDA was combined with network analysis to profile the individuals responsible for the births of new topics in the corpus. This reveals substantial asymmetries in inter-community influence. In figure 1, we show all of the affiliations for the members initiating a topic in each subreddit. R/MensRights emerges as a particularly influential hub, exerting notable thematic influence on both r/TheRedPill and r/MensLib. Yet r/MensRights itself remains comparatively impermeable, with limited uptake of topics originating from people with hybrid affiliation outside of r/TheRedPill. We further observe that nearly half of the most prominent topics within r/MensLib are introduced by “hybrid” users, i.e. individuals active in multiple subreddits, mainly r/PurplePillDebate and r/MensRights. When comparing the birth documents for each topic with the peak ones, we identify a significant proportion of hybrid users behind the birth documents, and mainly exclusive users for the peak documents. This entails that the themes introduced onto r/MensLib by users who have acquaintances with more radical communities are progressively integrated and reclaimed by exclusive members. We also find that the hybrid members introducing new topics into r/MensLib rank among the top 10% most central nodes in the other subreddits they intervene on.

These findings demonstrate that thematic flows across Reddit’s gender-oriented communities are not as diffuse or incidental as previously assumed. Instead, thematic transfer is largely driven by a small cohort of strategically positioned hybrid users who facilitate the migration of topics from one community to another. As exemplified here, the manosphere is not just loosely connected, it is an organized system of ideological diffusion and influence. Through the combined usage of topic modeling and network analysis, the behaviour of antifeminist activists can be tracked and profiled. The diachronous analysis can provide leads for the studies of online activism trajectories. Our next research objective would be to isolate those hybrid individuals and reconstruct their ideological and discursive paths by investigating ways in which their discourse evolves over time and determine whether or not a masculinist influencer profile can be outlined.

Figure 1: Thematic influence chord diagram

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